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Toward a new thinking of the eco-evolution for Eurasian otter (*Lutra lutra*): A review on the current research in Taiwan

Yu-Yang A. S. Chen

College of Science, National Taipei University of Education

This paper aims to review the research on Taiwan and Eurasian otters (*Lutra lutra*) in the past five years, and points out that: environment, region, species that predatory by otters, attacks by stray dogs and cats that have occurred frequently in recent years (Chen, 2023), or human-made land killings, etc. can all be used as the basis for Taiwan (in Kinmen area) in indicators of the evolutionary progress of the Eurasian otters (*Lutra lutra*).

The Eurasian otter (*Lutra lutra*) is the most widely distributed species (Conroy et al., 1998; Yoxon & Yoxon, 2019) (Figure 1), among the 13 existing otters (Yoxon & Yoxon, 2015) (Table 1), mainly concentrated in the European continent, the Mediterranean region, the southeast coast of China, Southeast Asia, and the entire southern Russia. In addition to the scattered habitat, the impact of the development of human society has also made the habitat of the *Lutra lutra* more trivial (Blench, 2022). In this context, *Lutra lutra* in different regions have begun to have their own survival coping modes. This paper focuses on the status of the otter species *Lutra lutra* in Taiwan. Within the territory of Taiwan, there has been no official record of *Lutra lutra* on Taiwan Island since 1990, and only Kinmen Island still has about 200 surviving individuals (Endemic Species Research Institute, COA, Executive Yuan, 2022). This paper, as a retrospective article, will review the research on *Lutra lutra* in Taiwan or Kinmen since 1996 (Lee, 1996). Due to space and research limitations, this article sorts out ten research papers or articles on Taiwan, Eurasian otters (*Lutra lutra*), and Kinmen in the past five years (2019-2023) and reviews the research in recent years to provide some insights into the future development of ecological conservation toward the new horizons.

In past five years, most of the studies on *Lutra lutra* focus on the corpses or casualties during the rescue process, while the living *Lutra lutra* focus on the distribution of habitats, which mostly rely on the information provided or reporting by eyewitnesses can be data. In addition, some studies have conducted genetic diversity analysis on *Lutra lutra* populations in Kinmen (Taiwan) and China, indicated that *Lutra lutra* located in Kinmen aren't isolated on the island population (Jang-Liaw et al., 2023). In addition, analyzing the diet of *Lutra lutra*, the selection behavior (the undigested food

in the body) can reflect the health indicator of *Lutra lutra* as an ecosystem (Jang-Liaw, 2021). While this indicator related to the state of the ecological environment (van Spronsen, 2020), the otters' survival aims a better environment (Dou et al., 2023). Apart from above, analysis of the reasons for the highly involved crisis of *Lutra lutra* in human society can be used to analyze the survival crisis of otters from the status of bites (scars) when rescuing (Li et al., 2020). The above items are the changes that *Lutra lutra* have coped with and produced in the process of individual evolution and can also be used as new ideas or approaches in the process of eco-conservation and eco-evolution in the future.

Table 1. 13 existing species of otters (Yoxon & Yoxon, 2015).

Genus	Species	As known as
Aonyx	<i>Aonyx capensis</i>	African clawless otter, Groot otter, Cape clawless otter
	<i>Aonyx congica</i>	Congo clawless otter, Cameroon clawless otter
	<i>Aonyx cinerea</i>	Asian small-clawed otter, Oriental small-clawed otter, Small-clawed otter, clawless otter
Enhydra	<i>Enhydra lutris</i>	Sea otter
Lontra	<i>Lontra canadensis</i>	River otter, North American river otter, Northern River otter
	<i>Lontra provocax</i>	Southern river otter
	<i>Lontra longicaudis</i>	Neotropical river otter, Neotropical otter
	<i>Lontra felina</i>	Marine otter
Lutra	<i>Lutra lutra</i>	Otter, Eurasian otter, European otter, Eurasian River otter, common otter, old world otter
	<i>Lutra sumatrana</i>	
Lutrogale	<i>Lutrogale perspicillata</i>	Smooth-coated otter
Pteronura	<i>Pteronura brasiliensis</i>	Giant otter, Giant River otter
Hydrictis	<i>Hydrictis maculicollis</i>	Spotted-necked otter, Speckle-throated otter

Figure 1. *Lutra lutra* distribution status (Thai National Parks, 2023)

Figure 2. The conservation promotion in Taiwan for *Lutra lutra*

Reference

1. Blench, R. M. (2022). *Do Formosanisms in Austronesian languages originate from a substrate of Taiwan's earliest inhabitants?* (Circulation draft). University of Cambridge. <https://reurl.cc/b9Gxrr>
2. Chen, Y.-Y. (2023, January). *Otters in Taiwan: The Situation of Distribution and Administration for Lutra lutra and Aonyx cinerea in Taiwan*. Paper presented at 2023 Congress of Animal Behavior & Ecology, Taichung, Taiwan. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7859441>

3. Conroy, J, Melisch, R., & Chanin, P. (1998). The Distribution and Status of the Eurasian Otter (*Lutra lutra*) in Asia - a Preliminary Review. IUCN/SCC Otter Specialist Group Bulletin, 15(1), 15-30.
https://www.iucnosgbull.org/Volume15/Conroy_et_al_1998.html
4. Dou, H., Wang, M., Yin, X., Feng, L., & Yang, H. (2023). Can the Eurasian otter (*Lutra lutra*) be used as an effective sampler of fish diversity? Using molecular assessment of otter diet to survey fish communities. *Metabarcoding and Metagenomics*, 7, e96733. <https://doi.org/10.3897/mbmg.7.96733>
5. Endemic Species Research Institute, Council of Agriculture, Executive Yuan (2022). *2023 Natural Ecology Handbook: I am on the road*. Endemic Species Research Institute, Council of Agriculture, Executive Yuan. [ISBN: 9399000040606] [GPN:1009103866]
6. Jang-Liaw, N.-H. (2021). A barcoding-based scat-analysis assessment of Eurasian otter *Lutra lutra* diet on Kinmen Island. *Ecology and Evolution*, 11(13), 8795-8813. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.7712>
7. Jang-Liaw, N.-H., Tan, Y.-C., Chang, C.-J., Juan, C.-H., Hou, H.-Y., Chung, L.-W., Cao, H.-S., Waku, D., Chang, S.-W., & Lee, L.-L. (2023). Genetic diversity and structure of Eurasian otters on Kinmen Island. *Conservation Genetics*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10592-023-01525-2>
8. Lee, L.-L. (1996). Status and distribution of river otters in Kinmen, Taiwan. *Oryx*, 30(3), 202-206. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605300021645>
9. Li, W.-T., Chiang, Y.-L., Chen, T.-Y., & Lai, C.-L. (2020). Pulmonary hair embolism in a rescued free-ranging Eurasian otter *Lutra lutra* in Kinmen, Taiwan. *Diseases of Aquatic Organisms*, 142, 55-61. <https://doi.org/10.3354/dao03532>
10. Thai National Parks. (2023). *European otter distribution*. Thai National Parks. Retrieved from <https://www.thainationalparks.com/species/european-otter> (Data visited: 12 June 2023)
11. van Spronsen, B. (2020). *Using habitat preferences of the Eurasian Otter (Lutra lutra) to predict future potential habitat after reintroduction in the Netherlands* [Unpublished master's thesis]. Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam.
<https://reurl.cc/aVaz79>
12. Yoxon, P., & Yoxon, G. (2015). *Otters of the World*. Whittles Publishing.
13. Yoxon, P., & Yoxon, B. (2019). Eurasian Otter (*Lutra lutra*): A review of the current world status. *OTTER, Journal of the International Otter Survival Fund*, 2019, 53-73. <https://reurl.cc/941yQd>